

University of Benin Students' Perception of Social Media Reports of Mohbad's Tragic Demise

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Abstract

This study was carried out to determine University of Benin students' perception of social media reports of Mohbad's tragic demise. The researcher employed a mixed study design and the data were collected with the use of questionnaire and interview guide. The data obtained from the questionnaire were analysed using frequency tables and straightforward percentages, while the data obtained from the interview were analysed using Yin's (1984) explanation building technique. The results showed that majority of the respondents were aware of the tragic demise of Mohbad and were equally up-to-date with the trends of the alleged demise. Findings also showed that the perception of the university of Benin students on social media reports of Mohbad tragic demise was biased and based on moral, ethical and religious inclinations, rather than legality. Based on the findings of this study, the researcher recommended that social media should engage in intensive and objective crime reportage to be able to truthfully and adequately cover stories in the right perspective for members of the society and that social media users should verify the authenticity, truthfulness and objectivity of related stories on their timeline through fact-finding alternatives before forming opinion and/or circulating such stories and media organisations and practitioner.

Keywords: Perception, Tragic Demise, University of Benin, Mohbad

Introduction

Social media have become an indisputable component of every social condition due to their ever-increasing reach and effect in today's culture. Even in the absence of a media trial, social media improve policymakers, managers and citizens' access to information, as well as the speed with which new information is collected, evaluated and communicated, allowing it to play a greater role in crime prevention (Asemah, Nwaoboli & Beli, 2022). A crime may be exacerbated or aided by the media. Despite this, the media's role in every crime, including social media users' dialectics and trials, cannot be neglected. Interacting with people or being social is a lifestyle activity that continues to evolve as society does. Interacting with one another is an age-old human action that refers to the human social environment connection. Interaction has occurred for a long

time prior to the development of technology and technology has evolved into a new social structure. The internet and social media in particular were born out of the transition into this new technological era (Akoh, 2011).

Social media and their tools influence what we think about, how we think about it and what, how and why they influence our emotions (Sarookhani, 2002). They spend about 6 hours each day on social media and they typically use numerous sites at the same time (Vannucci, Ohannessian & Gagnon, 2019). For quite some time, the enhanced and better use of social media platforms such as Facebook has become a worldwide phenomenon. Although, it began as a pastime for a few computer literates, it has evolved into a social norm and way of life for many individuals throughout the world (Nicole, 2007). Many individuals have identified these social media sites to be able to connect their friends, share Information, reinvent their identities and exhibit their social lives, according to Nicole (2007) and some social media users have low academic performance. However, social media's capabilities have expanded to include investigative reporting and criminal management. The public finds social networking sites appealing because they produce extremely devoted members and have some of the greatest retention rates among regular internet users (Berkley, 2007). Thus, this study was carried out to determine university of Benin students' perception of social media reports of Mohbad's tragic demise.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of the study were to:

1. Determine the extent of exposure to social media reports of Mohbad's tragic demise.
2. Fine out the social media channels through which university of Benin students were exposed to the reports of Mohbad's tragic death.
3. Ascertain the level of satisfaction with social media reports of Mohbad's death.
4. Find out the perception of university of Benin students on the social media reports of Mohbad's death.

Conceptualising Social Media

Social media are internet-based programmes that make it easier to create and share user-generated content (Kaplan & Haenlein, 2016). It was first used in 1979, when Tom Truscott and Jim Ellis of Duke University created Usenet, a worldwide discussion platform that allowed internet users to make open comments, according to Kaplan & Haelein (2010). The first time social media was openly recognised was on usenet. Using social media platforms, people create online communities where they may share knowledge, concepts, private messages and other kinds of material. Social media, which is another term for electronic communication, allows people to create online communities where they may share information, ideas, personal Messages and a number of other things (such as websites). According to Asemah, Illah & Edegoh (2013),

social media are the incorporation of digital media into a structured computerised environment that enables people to interact with the data for the right objectives. This includes electronic texts, images, moving pictures and sound. Digital media include things like music, moving visuals and electronic texts. Friends may respond to this statement by typing comments or like it (which is shown just below the status) and users can include whatever they want in their own statuses (Asemah, Nwaoboli, & Beli, 2022). As previously noted in this study and by researchers such as Asemah & Ekerikevwe (2013), social media are critical in the fight against crime. This is done by the examination and explanation of the effects of events on the lives and surrounding of the general public, as well as the repercussions of activities that contribute to societal insecurity (Asemah, Nwaoboli & Nwoko, 2022). These crime-specific platforms are part of the media's efforts to utilise exposure to raise awareness about the habits that lead to criminality (Nwabueze & Ebeze, 2013; Asemah, 2012).

Understanding Perception

Perception is the process of being aware of or comprehending sensory information. The Latin word 'perception,' which means receiving, gathering, activity of taking possession and apprehension with the mind or senses, is where the word "perception" comes from (Rao & Narayan, 2015). This Latin term served as the basis for the English word "perception." Quick & Nelson (2017) defined it as the act of processing information about another person or circumstance.

Mohbad's Death and the Cost of Fake News

In an era when information travels at the speed of a click, the tragic death of Nigerian rapper and singer Mohbad serves as a stark reminder of the perilous consequences of fake news. Born Ilerioluwa Aloba, MohBad, a talented artist who once graced the stage under Naira Marley's music label, Marlian records met an untimely demise that sent shockwaves through the music industry. However, what followed was a whirlwind of speculations and unverified claims. Ever since news broke of Mohbad's passing, a plethora of theories emerged, each a different cause of death. Even after the police exhumed remains for autopsy, his relentless churn of theories refused to cease.

Mohbad's proposing musical journey, marked by a debut EP titled 'Light' in 2020 and a subsequent departure from Naira Marley's label in 2022 to establish his own, *Imolenisation* has been overshadowed by disturbing allegations. Following his departure from Marlian Records World, it was reported that he was bullied by the singer Naira Marley and music promoter Sam Larry. Mohbad's untimely death and the subsequent surge of fake news underscore the critical need for media literacy in today's digital age.

Impact of Social Media on Perception of Bullying and Justice

Social media have become an important platform for communication and information sharing in modern society (Asemah, 2011a; Asemah, 2009; Asemah & Edegoh, 2013).

One area where social media have had a significant impact is the field of social crime and justice (Asemah-Ibrahim, Nwaoboli & Asemah, 2022b). Social media platforms allow for the rapid dissemination of information about crimes and legal proceedings, as well as providing a space for public discourse and debate. Social media have the potential to shape public opinion about crime and justice in several ways. The widespread availability of information on social media platforms means that individuals can quickly access news and updates about crimes and legal proceedings, even in real-time (Asemah-Ibrahim, Nwaoboli & Asemah, 2022a, 2022b). Social media also provide a space for individuals to express their opinions and engage in public discussions about these issues. As a result, social media can influence university of Benin residents' perceptions of bullying and justice, either by reinforcing existing beliefs or by introducing new perspectives (Nwaoboli & Asemah, 2021).

A study by Egbulefu & Nwaoboli (2023) found that social media can influence university of Benin residents' perceptions of the severity of bullying, with more sensationalised coverage leading to more negative perceptions. Social media can also impact media coverage of bullying and justice. The impact of social media on perceptions of bullying and justice can also extend to Legal proceedings. Social media conversations can potentially influence the fairness of legal proceedings by introducing biases or prejudicial information or by affecting public perceptions of the guilt or innocence of individuals involved in legal proceedings (Ekharefo & Nwaoboli, 2022, Asemah, Nwaoboli & Beli, 2022).

Studies have shown that social media can have a significant impact on legal proceedings. For example, a study by D'Agostino, Elia, Russo & Di Sanzo (2019) found that social media exposure to prejudicial information about a case can influence juror decision-making, potentially leading to unfair trials. Similarly, Nwaoboli & Asemah (2021) found that social media conversations can Influence public perceptions of the guilt or innocence of individuals involved in legal proceedings, potentially affecting their chances of a fair trial. Mohbad tragic demise is a serious global problem that affects many people, particularly those from vulnerable and disadvantaged communities and social media have become an important platform for individuals to express their opinions and views on different issues, including Mohbad's death. Studies have shown that exposure to social media comments about Mohbad's death can increase individuals' awareness and concern about the issue. For instance, D'Agostino, Elia, Russo & Di Sanzo (2019) found that social media comments positively influenced Participants' attitudes and willingness to take action against bullying.

Empirical Review

Asemah, Nwaoboli & Beli (2022) carried out a study on textual analysis of comments on select social media sites on Mohbad tragic demise case. The objectives of the study were to examine the Youtube and Facebook comments tied to Mohbad tragic demise, ascertain the frames of Youtube and Facebook comments on Mohbad tragic demised and examine

if the Youtube and Facebook dialectics of Mohbad demise and Media reports of Ilerioluwa olademeji contradict claims established by the Police. The study was anchored on the attribution theory.

Nwabueze & Ebeze (2013) investigated the crucial function played by the media in halting the rise in crime that has caused insecurity in Nigeria, particularly in the North, South Eastern and South Southern regions of the nation. The discourse used a qualitative analysis to evaluate the relationship between Nigeria's insecurity and the media, with special attention on useful practical solutions. According to Lenhart, Purcell, Smith & Zickuhr (2010), about 57% of social network users are 18-29 years old and have a personal profile on multiple social media websites. Quan-Haase & Young (2010), cited in Sponcil & Gitimu, (2013) found that 82% of college students reported logging into Facebook several times a day. Younger Students tended to use Facebook more frequently than older students to keep in touch with friends from high school or from their hometown (Pempek et al 2009, cited in Sponcil & Gitimu, 2013). When internet technology has surged in popularity, it is reasonable to be curious about its impact on human face-to-face communication. Baym, Zhang & Lin (2004), cited in Sponcil & Gitimu (2013) found that the quality and quantity of interactions in other media were not threatened by social internet sites. Studies conducted in Nigeria on internet use tend to yield similar findings. Dominick (2009) posits that social media network is like a map of specified ties such as friendship to which an individual is connected. Social networking sites include yahoo messenger, Facebook messenger, Blackberry messenger (BBM), Google talk, Google messenger, Iphone, Android and so on.

Igboaka & Hanson (2010) studied internet use in Ihiala, a rural Nigerian village. They found that internet users are mostly highly educated and that both students and business people use the internet for economic development purposes. Edegoh *et al* (2013) conducted a study on Facebook utilisation by students of Anambra State University. They found that students were heavy users of Facebook and that the gratifications they derive from using Facebook included chatting, information seeking and for academic purposes. Asemah & Nwaoboli (2021) conducted a survey which established that 78% Of Nigerians use social media on a daily basis with 66% being University students. Okonofua & Ewere (2018) examined the utilisation of social media for the campaign against cultism in the University of Lagos

Theoretical Framework

Attribution Theory

Attribution theory is a school of social psychology that attempts to explain how individuals determine the causes of events or behaviours as well as how that attribution influences future behaviour. Kelley (1967, 1973); Weiner *et al* (1971) and Weiner, Nierenberg & Goldstein (1976), as cited by Schmitt (2015) developed the fundamental theoretical frameworks first provided by Heider (1958). Attribution theory has now extended beyond social psychology to be used in a variety of management science areas.

Heider (1958) coined the term “naive Psychology,” which is based on attribution theory, which seeks to explain how laypeople determine the causes of specific events. This initial notion has spawned not one, but a slew of “attribution theories”. Two significant frameworks that have been widely recognised in academic.

Priming Theory

The phrase “priming” refers to the ways in which various forms of media have an impact on the decisions that members of the audience make. In 1982, Iyengar, Peters & Kender came up with the idea that would later be referred to as the priming effect (Asemah, Nwanmuo & Nkwa-Uwaoma, 2017). Priming is often considered to be the precursor of agenda setting, which is one of the concepts that the media influences. The associative network model of human memory, which is a subfield of cognitive psychology, forms the foundation for the concept of priming. The idea of media priming was inspired by the associative network model of human memory, in which an idea or concept is stored as a node in the network and is connected to other ideas or concepts via semantic pathways (Asemah, Nwanmuo & Nkwa-Uwaoma, 2017). Interpretative frame or premise for subsequent information processing or judgement formulation. Priming can also refer to the activation of a premise for subsequent information processing or judgement formulation.

Methodology

The researcher adopted the mixed research method for this study. The survey and the interview research methods were adopted for the study. The researcher chose the mixed research method because using one research design would not be enough to garner information for this type of research; thus, the interview design complemented lapses in the survey research design. The interview was used to get the perceptions of those whose works revolve around social media and crime such as journalists, lawyers and the police. The population of this study is university of Benin students in Ovia Local Government Area with a population of 77,000. In sum, the population of this study is 77,000. A sample size of 384 was taken from the population of the study. The sample for the study was gotten, using Krejcie & Morgan’s (1970) sample size calculation formula. For the survey, the research instrument for this study was the questionnaire. The interview guide was also another research instrument for the study. Purposively and simple random sampling techniques were used in this study.

Data Presentation and Analysis

Out of the three hundred and eighty four (384) copies of questionnaire distributed, only three hundred and seventy eight (378) copies were returned and found useful. The data of the data was, therefore, based on three hundred and seventy (378).

Table 1: Responses on Exposure to Social Media Reports of Mohbad’s Tragic Demise

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly agree	126	33.3
Agree	252	66.6
Neutral	0	0
Disagree	0	0
Strongly disagree	0	0
Total	378	100

Table 1 shows that all the respondents were aware of Mohbad tragic demise. This awareness of the case by university of Benin residents may not be unconnected with mass media's high reportage and analysis of the case when it happened.

Table 2: Level of Satisfaction with Social Media Reports of Mohbad's Tragic Death

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Very high	165	43.7
High	173	45.8
Neutral	0	0
Low	24	6.3
Very low	16	4.2
Total	378	100

The data in table 2 show that the respondents were satisfied with the social media reports of Mohbad's tragic death. The implication of this is that the case was highly publicised and that many university of Benin residents were highly informed and interested in the story

Discussion and Findings

This researcher investigated the awareness and perception of social media reports of Mohbad tragic demise among university of Benin students. The study sought to determine the views and opinions about social media reports of Mohbad's death, with particular focus on residents in university of Benin.

The findings showed a high level of exposure to the media reports on the death of Mohbad This high degree of exposure can be linked to the increasing number of social media users in Nigeria, especially amongst young people who constitute the largest demography of social media users in the world. This is in tandem with Ritzer & Jurgenson (2010) cited in Obar & Wildman (2015) who affirmed that with Web 2.0, internet users were turned from consumers to "prosumers," meaning they consume and make media contents. Similarly, Dijck (2012) added that these new capabilities enabled an upsurge in social media applications and dynamism; thus, allowing users to easily contact with one another and exchanging information, photographs and messages, amongst others. This is particularly significant given that technological determinism theory had established that people have very little free agency and as such they will

utilise whatever means of communication that society as a whole employs; hence, no matter what media they use, people will behave and feel the same way as long as they are utilising the same medium (Asemah, Nwanmuo & Nkwa-Uwaoma, 2015).

The findings showed that majority of the respondents are satisfied with social media reports of Mohbad's death and the extent of exposure to social media reports of the case was high due to the high number of respondents who affirmed that they were aware of the reports of Mohbad tragic demise. This supports the assertion of Nwabueze & Ebeze, (2013) that ordinary citizens may use social media to expose criminality and raise public awareness about terrorist attacks and the study of Banaji & Buckingham (2010) that social media are recognised for their conversation power across the world, which is vital in increasing public involvement on issues in the society. This is in tandem with the thrust of the cultivation analysis theory which asserts that people who utilise the media regularly are more likely to be affected by messages from the media (Asemah *et al* 2015) and as a result, the media are seen to have a role on how individuals perceive social reality on their own (Cooren, Kuhn, Cornelissen & Clark, 2011).

Conclusion and Recommendations

The findings showed that the respondents were highly exposed to social media reports of the tragic death of Mohbad. Thus, the researcher recommend that social media should be used as great tools in advocating for perpetrators of evil, such as crime case to be brought to book, not considering their social status. Social media platforms can be leveraged on and also give opportunity to those that do have a voice to seek for justice and there is need for encouraged collaboration between different social media platforms for comprehensive coverage of national significance events, leveraging collective resources and expertise.

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